

WHAT DRIVES THE PURCHASE DECISION IN INSTAGRAM STORES?

Questionnaire

Construct	Question	Factor loading	Cronbachs Alpha	Source
Peer Customer Endorsement	Instagram shows reviews from satisfied customers.	0,715	0,714	Che et al. (2017)
	I can see from the comments on Instagram stores that existing customers are satisfied.	0,813		
	I believe that Instagram customer reviews are to be taken as true.	0,912		
	Customer feedback in Instagram stores will improve my online shopping experience.	0,907		
Perceived Security Control	Instagram merchants implement security measures to protect their customers.	0,904	0,771	Cheung and Lee (2006)
	Instagram merchants have the ability to verify their customers' identities for security purposes.	0,897		
	Instagram merchants ensure that transaction-related data is protected during the transaction.	0,926		
Perceived Privacy Control	Instagram merchants do not sell my personal information to third parties without consent. *	0,852	0,745	Cheung and Lee (2006)
	Instagram merchants care about the privacy of their customers.	0,950		
	Instagram merchants will not disclose customer personal information.	0,898		
Personal Recommendation	Based on the information on my Instagram profile, I will be shown product ads that match my preferences.	0,847	0,683	Mikalef et al. (2017)
	Products presented on Instagram are customized according to my needs.	0,882		
	Product recommendations on Instagram make me feel like an important customer.	0,896		
Trust	I trust that sellers on Instagram always consider customer interests in the best possible way.	0,843	0,824	Che et al. (2017)
	I classify Instagram shopping as trustworthy.	0,874		
	I think sellers on Instagram don't want to take advantage of their customers.	0,881		
	I believe that Instagram stores keep their promises and commitments.	0,897		
	I trust that information on Instagram is true.	0,879		
Usability	On Instagram, it is easy to find the information needed to make a purchase.	0,921	0,712	Alonso-Dos-Santos et al. (2020)
	The structure and content on Instagram is easy to understand.	0,828		
	The organization of content on Instagram allows me to navigate different pages.	0,911		
	I always feel like I control what I do when using Instagram.	0,697		
Buying Intention	I am thinking about making purchases on Instagram.	0,955	0,896	Che et al. (2017); Brock et al. (2011)
	I intend to use an Instagram store to make purchases in the near future.	0,959		
	I would recommend the use of an Instagram store to others.	0,948		

* reverse measured construct

References

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